

The Theory of the "Death of the Author" in Visual Arts and "Appropriation Art" in the Postmodern Era

Mehdi Nasiri: Ph.D. Candidate, Department of Comparative and Analytical History of Islamic Art, Faculty of Theoretical Sciences and Advanced Studies in Art, Iran University of Art, Tehran, Iran (nasiri.mehdi@ut.ac.ir).

Introduction:

The field of visual arts during the postmodern era encountered fundamental changes that influenced not only the methods of creating artworks but also the concepts and theories related to art. One of these significant shifts is the theory of the "Death of the Author," which has extensively impacted the realm of Appropriation Art. This essay first examines visual arts in the postmodern era, then explores the Death of the Author theory and its influence on appropriation, and finally investigates the concept of artistic appropriation within postmodernism.

"Appropriation Art" refers to the process wherein artists utilize existing cultural and artistic elements or artworks to create a new piece. This practice is rooted in early 20th-century art movements like Dadaism and Surrealism, but it reached its zenith during the postmodern era. By employing recognizable images, symbols, and elements, postmodern artists decontextualized them from their original settings and placed them within new structures. This allowed new meanings to be ascribed to them, prompting audiences toward varied interpretations of the works. Appropriation enabled artists to re-present classical and contemporary artworks in novel, creative ways. It also allowed them to convey social and political messages in a satirical or critical manner by leveraging well-known cultural and artistic elements.

Postmodernism and Visual Arts:

Postmodernism is an intellectual and cultural movement that emerged in the West in the late 1960s. This movement arose as a reaction against modernism and its tenets across various fields, including art, architecture, literature, cinema, and philosophy. Postmodernists challenged

concepts such as "absolute truth," "linear logic," and "metanarratives," emphasizing instead relativism, polyphony, and differences. In the visual arts, postmodernism stressed pluralism and freedom of expression. Postmodern artists questioned modernist rules and traditions, seeking new modes of self-expression. They employed diverse techniques such as collage, assemblage, Pop Art, Op Art, photorealism, and conceptual art to convey their messages.

Postmodernists believed that absolute truth does not exist and that meanings are shaped within diverse cultural and linguistic contexts. In the visual arts, postmodernism led to the emergence of works that dismantled traditional boundaries between genres and media. Postmodern artists pursued self-awareness, linguistic and stylistic play, and the critique of accepted concepts. Through the method of appropriation, they sought to create new artworks. Appropriation in postmodernism meant that rather than expressing a single truth, the artist depicted their personal narratives and individual experiences. Art was no longer a final product, but an evolving process for discovering pluralistic meanings and engaging in dialogue with the audience. Table 1 outlines some core characteristics of appropriation art in the postmodern era.

<p>Appropriation:</p>	<p>The artist intentionally uses existing cultural and artistic works or elements, recreating or reproducing them in their own work. This can manifest as a direct quotation of another piece, the use of specific cultural symbols, or the creation of a new version of a renowned work.</p>
<p>Intertextuality:</p>	<p>Every literary or non-literary text interacts with other texts, and no new text is created without links to prior ones. In appropriation art, intertextuality implies that every artwork is somewhat influenced by preceding artworks and its surrounding socio-cultural environment. When creating, an artist typically draws inspiration from, or dialogues with, the elements, styles, themes, or symbols of other artists' works.</p>
<p>Parody:</p>	<p>The artist recreates a recognized work, style, or element in a satirical manner to criticize or mock it. In parody, the artist deliberately manipulates, exaggerates, or distorts prominent features of a famous work or style to render it humorous and absurd. Parody is a powerful tool in appropriation for critiquing and challenging dominant societal values and discourses.</p>

<p>Depthlessness (Shallowness):</p>	<p>This refers to artworks lacking depth, complexity, and semantic dimension, focusing solely on visual and superficial aspects. This depthlessness is sometimes raised as a critique of modern and contemporary art, which some view as devoid of content and purely reliant on form. However, in many cases, this simplicity and visual focus is a deliberate artistic choice.</p>
<p>Eclecticism:</p>	<p>Eclecticism in appropriation implies that the artist combines diverse and sometimes contradictory artistic elements, styles, and methods. This approach is undertaken to achieve artistic novelty, to express the complexities and contradictions of modern society, or out of a passion for experimentation. Prominent examples include Picasso's Cubist works and Andy Warhol's Pop Art.</p>

Table 1: Core Characteristics of Appropriation Art in the Postmodern Era

The postmodern movement emphasized freedom of artistic expression and the critique of dominant culture. Artists in this style utilized "reproduction, rearrangement, and resignification" to decontextualize prior works and place them in a new text. This ranges from the direct use of existing images to the amalgamation of various objects and phenomena within a new structure. The artist's motive can be critical, satirical, or purely a novel conceptual recreation. Table 2 presents prominent postmodern artists who utilized appropriation techniques to create artworks.

<p>Andy Warhol:</p>	<p>A pioneer of Pop Art, Warhol used popular culture imagery, such as Campbell's Soup Cans and Hollywood stars, to create works critiquing consumer and media culture.</p>
<p>Marcel Duchamp:</p>	<p>A pioneer of this approach, Duchamp challenged concepts of artistic originality with famous works like "Fountain" and "L.H.O.O.Q.".</p>
<p>Sherrie Levine:</p>	<p>By reproducing famous artworks, such as paintings by Claude Monet and Kazimir Malevich, Levine created works that challenged concepts of originality and ownership in art. She shifted focus from the artist to the audience, demonstrating that the meaning of an</p>

	artwork is formed in the process of its reading and interpretation by the audience.
Robert Rauschenberg:	"Erased de Kooning Drawing," in which Rauschenberg erased a piece by Willem de Kooning, is recognized as a prominent example of appropriation art.
Barbara Kruger:	Known for utilizing media imagery and critiquing popular culture.
Cindy Sherman:	Parodic illustration of consumer culture stereotypes.
Richard Prince:	With his "Gangster" series reconstructed from old images, he questioned the traditional idea of artistic ownership. He demonstrated that an artwork can find new meaning through the rereading and manipulation of others' works.

Table 2: Prominent Postmodern Artists and Their Use of Appropriation

The Theory of the Death of the Author and Appropriation Art:

The "Death of the Author" is a concept introduced by French philosopher Roland Barthes in a 1967 essay. Barthes argues that in an era of mass production and mass media, the traditional concept of the author as the unique creator of an artwork is no longer valid. Instead of viewing the text as the product of a single creator's mind, it must be seen as the product of multiple cultural discourses and codes in which it was produced. Undoubtedly, the emergence of this theory caused a massive revolution in art criticism and the visual arts. By challenging traditional paradigms that positioned the artist or writer as the primary source and determinant of a work's meaning, it paved the way for new, pluralistic interpretations. By positing that a literary or artistic work is a polyphonic fabric woven from various texts, whose meaning is formed in the reading process by the reader/viewer, Barthes laid the groundwork for new art movements emphasizing the audience's role in meaning production. One such movement heavily influenced by Barthes

was "Appropriation Art". Barthes challenges the traditional, authoritarian role of the author in interpreting and understanding a work. He articulates the core ideas of this theory as follows:

- **Author:** The traditional creator whose identity, experiences, and intentions influence the interpretation of the text.
- **Work:** Barthes believes a literary work should not be viewed as the unique expression of a single author, but as a polyphonic fabric composed of various texts.
- **Text:** For Barthes, the text is an endless tissue of signifiers with no fixed, predetermined meaning. Its meaning is shaped by the reader during the reading process.
- **Reader:** Barthes considers the reader's role crucial in creating the work's meaning. The reader is no longer a passive consumer, but an active producer who constructs the text's meaning during the reading process.

Ultimately, Barthes calls for the author's role to be sidelined in the interpretation of a literary work, allowing meaning to form during the reading process by the reader. This liberates the reader from the author's authority, enabling them to discover new, pluralistic meanings within the work. In truth, postmodern artists, inspired by Barthes's theory, challenged the notions of originality and innovation in art, demonstrating that a new artwork can be created through the rereading, alteration, and manipulation of prior works. They discarded the author–artist as the primary source and determinant of the artwork's meaning, focusing instead on the audience's reading and interpretation. From this perspective, it can be said that Barthes's *Death of the Author* provided a crucial theoretical foundation for justifying and understanding this art movement in the postmodern era. By challenging artistic authority and ownership, the theory emphasized the reader–viewer's role in meaning creation—the exact goal postmodern artists pursued by recreating and rereading the works of others. By questioning traditional concepts such as originality, creativity, and artistic ownership, this movement demonstrated that an artwork is no longer a fixed, unique product of a single artist, but a dynamic, evolving process whose meaning is determined through its reading and interpretation.

Appropriation Art: Appropriation art is an expressive method in visual arts where the artist incorporates existing works, with or without slight alterations, into the context of a new work. Rooted in 1960s postmodern movements and influenced by Barthes's *Death of the Author*, this approach challenges intellectual property and the original creator's rights. In Persian, artistic appropriation corresponds to terms such as artistic adaptation, tracing, acquisition, derivation, and borrowing.

Appropriation art signifies the use of styles, themes, narratives, and other artistic subtexts developed in different cultural contexts. This can include elements from various cultures utilized creatively or non-creatively in new works. The primary structure of appropriation can be divided into two categories:

- **Derivative Appropriation (Non-Innovative):** In this method, the artist attempts to remain faithful to the original culture's standards, repeating the artistic content exactly as it exists originally. Due to a lack of familiarity with the cultural and semantic contexts of the original content, this can lead to incomplete and inauthentic works. For example, a Western artist attempting to perform Peking opera without understanding its cultural and semantic background.
- **Transformative Appropriation (Innovative):** In this style, the artist uses elements from another culture but applies them in novel, innovative ways absent in the original culture. This method can result in original works with significant aesthetic value. For instance, Pablo Picasso incorporated African sculptural elements into his enduring work "Les Femmes d'Alger (O.J.)", innovatively merging them with his own style.

Dadaist artist Marcel Duchamp was the first to draw a mustache on Leonardo da Vinci's famous painting "Mona Lisa" in 1919 and exhibit it. Titled "L.H.O.O.Q.", Duchamp's piece is considered one of the earliest examples of appropriation art, where an artist transforms a recognized artwork into a new piece by adding or altering elements. Duchamp's action was highly controversial at the time and sparked extensive debate regarding the nature of art.

Image 2: L.H.O.O.Q., by Marcel Duchamp, 1919.

Image 1: Mona Lisa, by Leonardo da Vinci, 1503 to 1506

In 1957, Pablo Picasso also created a work based on Diego Velázquez's painting "Las Meninas". Although it somewhat adhered to the main structure, it possessed significant differences.

Image 4: Las Meninas (The Maids of Honor), by Pablo Picasso, oil on canvas (Cubist style), 1957, 194 × 260 cm, Location: Museu Picasso (Barcelona, Spain).

Image 3: Las Meninas (The Family of Philip IV), by Diego Velázquez, 1656, oil, 318 × 276 cm, Location: Museo del Prado, Madrid.

Another famous work subjected to rewriting and artistic appropriation was Leonardo da Vinci's "The Last Supper". Artists such as Salvador Dalí created their own works based on this painting.

Image 5: The Last Supper, by Leonardo da Vinci, 1495 to 1498, mural painting with tempera and oil on plaster, 460 × 880 cm, Location: Santa Maria delle Grazie church, Milan, Italy .

Image 6: The Last Supper, by Salvador Dalí, 1955, oil on canvas, 247.7 × 194.3 cm, Location: Museu Nacional d'Art de Catalunya (National Art Museum of Catalonia), Barcelona, Spain .

Conclusion:

The discourse on artistic appropriation profoundly impacted visual arts in the postmodern era. This movement allowed artists to formulate new ideas regarding the nature of art, the artist's role, and the relationship between art and society. It also contributed to the emergence of new art schools in the art world. Postmodern artists challenged the concept of originality by utilizing and reconstructing existing images and ideas. This raised questions about what makes an artwork original and what the artist's role in the creation of an artwork truly is. On the other hand, the discussion of appropriation helped expand the boundaries of what was recognized as an artwork. This led to the acceptance of new expressive forms such as conceptual art, performance art, and installation art. Through the process of appropriation in art, artists critiqued popular culture and consumer society. Furthermore, appropriation art evolved into a powerful tool for examining social and political issues, as well as social subjugation. In addition to these points, Roland Barthes's Death of the Author theory profoundly influenced the concept of appropriation during postmodernism. Barthes believed that a text should not merely be a reflection of the author's

intent and purpose, but that the audience plays an active role in creating meaning and interpreting the work. From this perspective, the artist is no longer the sole, central source of meaning; rather, the audience plays a key role in the appropriation process. This approach shifts power away from the artist and entrusts it to the audience to extract multiple meanings from the work themselves. Therefore, the realm of appropriation art in the postmodern era was considered a polyphonic process, liberated from authorial authority, which invited the audience's active participation in the creation of meaning.

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